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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTIOXIDANT
INFUSED COLD CREAM**

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Abstract:

Cold creams are widely used for their moisturizing and protective properties, providing a barrier against harsh environmental conditions. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a cold cream infused with natural antioxidants to enhance skin health and provide additional anti-aging benefits. The antioxidants were derived from natural sources such as green tea extract, vitamin E, and essential oils known for their skin-protective properties.

The cold cream was formulated using an oil-in-water emulsion system, incorporating ingredients like beeswax, almond oil, and glycerin for optimal skin hydration and emollience. The antioxidant blend was optimized for stability and compatibility within the formulation. Evaluation parameters included physicochemical properties such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, and stability under various storage conditions. Additionally, the formulation was assessed for its antioxidant activity using DPPH radical scavenging assays and skin compatibility through patch tests.

The results demonstrated that the antioxidant-infused cold cream exhibited excellent stability, satisfactory moisturizing properties, and significant antioxidant activity. Skin compatibility studies revealed no signs of irritation or adverse effects, making it suitable for all skin types. This study highlights the potential of combining cosmetic and therapeutic benefits in skincare formulations, offering enhanced functionality for consumers.

***Keywords: Cold cream, antioxidants, skincare, natural extracts, formulation development, stability evaluation**

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INTRODUCTION:

A cosmetic is defined under Section 3 of the Drugs and Cosmetics Act (India), 1940, as any substance intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on, inserted into, or otherwise applied to the human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance. This definition also includes any article intended for use as a component of a cosmetic^[1].

The use of herbal products as cosmetics remains as wide spread to day as it was in ancient times. Herbal cosmetics are primarily favored due to their minimal or non-existent side effects compared to synthetic products, and they often exhibit enhanced effects upon application. These beauty products, made from herbal ingredients, enhance and condition the properties of the skin. All herbal extracts used in these formulations are derived from natural plant sources, avoiding harmful synthetic drugs. Chemical or synthetic drugs/APIs are excluded from these preparations to prevent various skin issues. The concept of herbal cosmetics was established long ago in various systems of medicine, including Rig-Veda, Yajur veda, Ayurveda, Unani, and Homeopathy^[2].

COSMETICS AND COSMACEUTICALS

The term is attributed to Dr. Albert Kligman, who recognized a hybrid category of products lying on the spectrum between drugs and cosmetics. It is now commonly used to describe a cosmetic product that provides a pharmaceutical therapeutic benefit, though it may not necessarily offer a biological therapeutic benefit. The demand for cosmeceuticals is rapidly increasing due to the availability of new ingredients, financial incentives for developing successful products, and consumers's need for formulations that maintain high-quality standards. The plant parts used in cosmetic preparations must meet this demand and require a better understanding of skin physiology^[3].

CREAMS

Topical medications that can be applied to the skin are called creams. A cream is a homogeneous, viscous, or semi-solid preparation with a relatively fluid consistency, intended for external application to the skin or certain mucous membranes for protective, therapeutic, or preventive purposes, especially when an occlusive effect is not necessary. Creams are

defined as “a semisolid dosage form containing one or more drug substances dissolved or dispersed in a suitable base.” They are formulated using hydrophilic or hydrophobic bases to create preparations that are essentially miscible with skin secretions^[4].

Creams are considered pharmaceutical products as they are prepared using techniques developed in the pharmaceutical industry. They serve a variety of cosmetic functions, including washing, beautifying, enhancing appearance, and providing protection, as well as therapeutic purposes. Creams can be ayurvedic, herbal, or allopathic, and are used by people according to their needs and skin conditions^[5].

TYPES OF SKIN CREAMS

They are divided into two types:

Oil-in-Water (O/W) Creams:

These creams consist of tiny oil droplets distributed throughout a continuous aqueous phase. An oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion is one in which the oil is dispersed as droplets within the water phase^[6].

Water-in-Oil (W/O) Creams:

These creams consist of tiny water droplets scattered throughout an oily phase. A water-in-oil (W/O) emulsion is characterized by water as the dispersed phase and oil as the dispersion medium^[7].

THE ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF SKIN:

The integumentary system was coined from the Latin term “integument” which means “body covering”, comprises of skin and other accessory structures such as hair, nails, glands, muscles and blood vessels. Skin considered to be the largest external part in the human body, covers 12-16% of adults body weight^[8]. Dermatology is a branch of medical science that deals with the research, diagnosis and treatment of skin diseases^[9]. The skin acts as a protective barrier, protecting it from the external climate and also protecting underlying structure from damage and microbial invasion. There are many cellular components such as melanocyte, red blood cells and keratinocytes^[10]. Cosmetics are used to improve the appearance of skin changes associated with pigmentation, wrinkling and sagging^[11].

Fig.1:AnatomyofSkin

The skin comprises of three primary layers namely,

1. Epidermis
2. Dermis
3. Hypodermis.

ANTIOXIDANTS:

An antioxidant may be defined as any substance by which the oxidation of a substrate can be delayed or prevented when it is present in small amounts relative to the amount of the substrate. Antioxidants or free radical scavenger function as molecular protectors, potentially preventing cellular damage caused by volatile free radical compounds that might otherwise accelerate premature aging, triggers inflammatory responses and other cutaneous issues^[22,23].

VARIOUS TYPES OF ANTIOXIDANTS:

Free radicals, which can damage cells through oxidative stress, are counteracted by antioxidants in multiple ways. These protective compounds are prevalent in nature, especially in herbs, plant-derived foods such as fruits, vegetables, nuts and whole grains. Antioxidants can be characterized as natural, synthetic, dietary, endogenous and exogenous antioxidants play a vital role^[24].

DIETARY ANTIOXIDANTS:

It includes,

- Vitamins like vitamin-C and vitamin-E rich in citrus, strawberries, tomatoes, green vegetables, plant-based oils and avocados.
- Minerals like copper, iron, selenium,

manganese and zinc rich in red meat, poultry, seafood, legumes, fortified grains etc.

- Carotenoids like α -carotene, β -carotene, β -cryptoxanthin and lycopene rich in pumpkin, papaya, carrot, spinach and red pepper etc.
- Phenolic compounds like hydroxyl benzoic acid and hydroxyl cinnamic acid rich in tea, coffee, strawberry and grape juice etc.
- Flavonoids like flavanols, flavones, isoflavones, flavanones and antho-cyanins etc.
- Also includes lignans, stilbenes and organo sulfur compounds like iso-thiocyanates, indoles and allylic sulphur compounds^[25].

SYNTHETICANTIOXIDANTS:

Synthetic antioxidants are man-made compounds designed to preventors low down oxidation in various products, particularly in food, cosmetics and industrial applications. They serve a similar function to natural antioxidants but are created in laboratories to enhance stability, effectiveness or to reduce costs.

Based on mechanism of action it is classified into two types:

- ✓ Primary antioxidants
- ✓ Secondary antioxidants.

Examples, Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA), Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), Tertiary butylhydroquinone (TBHQ), Propyl gallate, Ethoxyquin [26].

NATURAL ANTIOXIDANTS:

Natural antioxidants are found in nature, primarily in plants, but also in some animals and microorganisms. They are not synthetically produced in a laboratory. These compounds work by donating electrons to unstable molecules (free radicals), thereby neutralizing them and preventing them from causing oxidative damage to cells. It includes, Vitamins (e.g., Vitamin C, Vitamin E), Polyphenols (e.g., flavonoids, tannins), Carotenoids (e.g., beta-carotene, lycopene), Minerals (e.g., selenium, zinc). Natural antioxidants are believed to play a role in preventing or delaying various health issues, including skin aging, by protecting cells from oxidative stress [27].

ENDOGENOUS ANTIOXIDANTS:

Endogenous antioxidants are substances naturally produced within the body that neutralize harmful free radical and reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can damage cellular components like DNA, proteins and lipids. Endogenous antioxidants are of two types namely,

1. Enzymatic antioxidants: It includes catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPX), peroxiredoxin, thioredoxin and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase.
2. Non-enzymatic antioxidants: It includes glutathione, uric acid, bilirubin, phenolic, serum albumin, transferrin, lipoic acid and ferritin [28].

EXOGENOUS ANTIOXIDANTS:

Exogenous antioxidants are substances that are obtained from external sources, typically through diet or supplementation, to help and protect the body against oxidative stress and free radical damage. It includes Vitamin C (ascorbic acid/ascorbate), vitamin E (tocopherols, tocotrienols), carotenoids (α -carotene, β -carotene, zeaxanthin, lutein, lycopene, β -cryptoxanthin), polyphenols (flavanols, anthocyanins, isoflavones, phenolic acid) and trace elements (selenium, zinc) [29].

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Antioxidants protect biological systems through two primary mechanisms. First, they can directly neutralize free radicals by donating electrons, effectively breaking the chain of oxidative reactions. Second, they can remove or deactivate reactive

oxygen or nitrogen species before these can trigger damaging processes. Beyond these core mechanisms, antioxidants influence biological systems in several ways. They transfer electrons, bind harmful metal ions, work synergistically with other antioxidants and regulate genes involved in oxidative stress responses. This complex approach allows antioxidants to provide comprehensive protection against oxidative damage, maintaining cellular health and function. The versatility of antioxidant action underscores their importance in biological systems, where they serve as key protectors against the potentially harmful effects of oxidative stress. The DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) test is a widely used method for measuring antioxidant activity of substances [30].

FUNCTIONS OF ANTIOXIDANTS:

1. The risk of developing various chronic conditions, including heart ailments, ocular diseases, accelerated aging and malignancies can be reduced by consuming a diet abundant in antioxidants [31].
2. Boosting Collagen Synthesis: Certain antioxidants, notably Vitamin C, stimulate collagen production. This process enhances skin elasticity and helps diminish the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles [32].
3. Mitigating Skin Discoloration: Antioxidants inhibit the overproduction of melanin, facilitating the gradual lightening of hyperpigmented areas [33].
4. Pacifying Skin Irritation: Antioxidants, especially polyphenols, exhibit potent anti-inflammatory capabilities. These properties effectively reduce skin redness and discomfort [34].
5. Preventing environmental damage: Antioxidants shield the skin from pollutants, toxins and other external factors that can lead to skin damage and deterioration [35].

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM OF THE PROJECT:

The aim of this project is to formulate and evaluate the poly herbal anti-oxidant cold cream using the extracts of pumpkin pulp, hibiscus flower and rosemary oil.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To carry out the extraction of the selected herbal material.
2. To formulate a cold cream using the pumpkin pulp extract, hibiscus flower extract and rosemary

oil.

3. To evaluate the cold cream to determine their antioxidant properties.
4. To carry out the evaluation aspects of cold cream such as FTIR studies, homogeneity, wash ability, pH, irritancy, spread ability and after feel.

Pumpkin *Cucurbita pepo*, Hibiscus *Rosa sinensis* and Rosemary *Salvia rosmarinus* were gathered from the neighbourhoods of Bengaluru, Karnataka. The plants were identified and authenticated by taxonomist at Central Ayurveda Research Institute, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

Analytical grades of Borax, Bees wax, Liquid paraffin, methyl paraben, and propyl paraben were obtained for the formulation.

COLLECTION OF MATERIALS

DRUGPROFILE 1} HIBISCUS

Biological Source: *Rosa sinensis*

Family: Malvaceae

Synonyms: *Hibiscus arnottii*, *H. boryanus*, *H. cooperi*, *H. festalis*, *H. liliiflorus*, *H. rosiflorus*

[37]

Habitat: India is probably its place of origin, though the Arabs assert it came from Spain^[38].

Plant description: This plant requires moderate temperature and high humidity for the best growth. It is a perennial shrub consist of tap root system Leaves are ovate or lanceolate and flowers are pedicillate. Different parts of plants have antioxidant, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory and hepatoprotective activity^[39].

Chemical constituents: Tannins, steroids, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins. It mainly contains quercetin, β -sitosterol, riboflavin and thiamine^[40].

Fig.2: *Hibiscus Rosa sinensis*

2} PUMPKIN

Biological Source: *Cucurbita pepo*

Family: Cucurbitaceae

Synonyms: *Cucumis pepo*, *C. citrullus*, *C. auratia*, *C. cougero*, *C. esculenta*

Habitat: It is native to Northern Mexico or Columbia. It is mainly seen in Nigeria. It also exists in Europe and Asia^[41].

Plant description: *C. pepo* is an annual creeping or climbing plant having shallow, branched tap root system varies in size and shape. Fruits are variable in size and gives pale yellow to crimson colour. Pumpkin seeds contain high amount of vitamins, minerals and antioxidants. Pumpkin pulp is used in the treatment of intestinal inflammation, dyspepsia, jaundice and stomach disorders^[42].

Chemical Constituents: Carotenoids, minerals, dietary fibres, β -carotene, para-aminobenzoic acid, polysaccharides, syringic acid, vitamin A, vitamin E, vitamin C, tannins^[43].

Fig.3: *Cucurbitapepo***3}ROSEMARY:****Biological Source:** *Salvia Rosmarinus***Family:** Lamiaceae**Synonyms:** *R. angustifolius, R. communis, R. flexuosus, R. latifolius, R. ligusticus, R. palau,*
*R. prostrates, R. rigidus, R. tenuifolius, Salvia fasciculata***Habitat:** It is indigenous to the Mediterranean region, along with Portugal and northwestern Spain.**Plant description:** Rosemary is indeed a fragrant, evergreen shrub that belongs to the mint family. It features needle-like leaves that are often used for their aromatic properties. The plant produces two-lipped, purplish-blue and white flowers. The transition from soft to wood systems helps the plant support its structure as it grows taller and more robust over time. In folk medicine, it has been employed as an antispasmodic, mild analgesic and for the treatment of intercostal neuralgia, headaches, migraine, insomnia, emotional upset and depression.**Chemical constituents:** α -pinene, 1, 8-cineole, camphor, borneol, rosmarinic acid, rosmanol, Carnosol, Rosmaridiphenol-15, Rosemariquinine-16, Carnosic acid. About 90% of anti-oxidant property is due to high phenolic content such as carsonic acid, rosmarinic acid, carnosol, rosmanol, rosmariquinine, rosemariidiphenol^[44].Fig.4: *Salvia rosmarinus*

4.3 EXCIPENTS USED:**1) BORAX:**

IUPAC name: Sodium tetra borate dehydrate

Molecular formula: $B_4H_{20}Na_2O_{17}$

Synonyms: Sodium borate, Sodium diborate, Sodium Meta borate, Komex, Disodium borate heptahydrate, Disodium borate monohydrate, Monosodium metaborate.

Molecular weight: 381.4g/mol **Color:** White, crystalline solid

Taste: Alkaline

Boiling point: 608°F

Melting point: 75°C **Density:**

1.73 g/cm³

Solubility: Soluble in water and insoluble in ethanol.

Uses: Borax is mainly used as emulsifying agent and stabilizer. It prevents the growth microbes and stabilizes the pH and prevents the spoiling of cosmetics. It is a common component for cleanser and toners for its alkaline nature. Borax can also be used as buffering agent and preservative in cosmetic [45].

Structure:

Fig.5: Structure of Borax

2) BEES WAX

IUPAC Name: Triacontanyl palmitate

Synonyms: White bees wax, yellow bees wax, Cera Alba, Cera flava, Hydroxyl, Rodex

Molecular formula: $C_{15}H_{31}COOC_{30}H_{61}$

Molecular weight: 169.178g/mol

Color: Yellow or white **Odor:**

Odor of honey **Taste:** Faint

balsamic **Melting point:** 61-65°C

Density: 0.95-0.96g/cm³

Solubility: Soluble in chloroform, ether, fixed oil, sparingly soluble in ethanol and insoluble in water.

Uses: Due to its elastic property, beeswax enhances kinelasticity. These have anti-allergenic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial and germicidal activity. In cosmetics, it is used as thickener, when used along with borax, it acts as emulsifier. It can be used as stiffening agent and enhance the viscosity of cold cream. It can also provide humectant and emollient property for skin ^[46].

Fig.6:StructureofBeeswax

3}LIQUID PARAFFIN:

IUPAC name: 2-(3, 4, 5-trihydroxyphenyl) chromenylium-3, 5, 7-triol; chloride

Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₁ClO₇

Synonyms: Paraffinumliquidum, paraffinoil, liquidparaffinoil, Russian mineraloil

Molecular weight: 338g/mol

Color: Colorless

Odor: Odorless

Boiling point: 310°C

Melting point: -9-18°C

Density: 0.85g/ml

Solubility: Insoluble in Water and alcohol, slightly soluble in dehydrated alcohol and freely soluble in chloroform, ether and volatile oil.

Uses: It is used in the formulation of skin creams as it enhances skin moisture and acts as a barrier for skin ^[47].

Structure:

Fig.7:StructureofLiquidParaffin

4)PROPYL PARABEN**IUPACname:** Propyl 4-hydroxybenzoate**Molecular formula:** C₁₀H₁₂O₃ **Synonym:** Propyl-p-hydroxybenzoate **Molecular weight:**

180.2g/mol

Color: White or colorless**Odor:** Odorless or faint aromatic**Taste:** Tasteless or numbs to tongue **Melting****point:** 95-98°C**Density:** 1.73g/cm³**Solubility:** Soluble in acetone, isopropanol, ethanol, methanol, ethyl acetate**Uses:** It is used as a preservative which enhances the stability of the skin products. It is used along with the other parabens.**Structure:**

Fig.8: Structure of Propyl Paraben

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE:**1. CUCURBITA PEPO:**

Fresh pumpkins were bought from a local market and cleaned with water. The skins and seeds were removed and the pumpkin flesh was sliced into pieces and air-dried. Next, it was ground into fine powders and sifted through a 150-mesh screen. This powder underwent Soxhlet extraction with ethanol at 40°C. The resulting yield was heated to remove the ethanol, yielding a thick, adhesive substance that was dissolved in distilled water for further formulation.

Fig.10: Extraction of Cucurbita pepo

HIBISCUS ROSA SINENSIS:

Hibiscus Rosa sinensis harvested locally was dried in the shade, finely powdered and sieved through a 150-mesh sieve. The powdered material underwent extraction via maceration. Subsequently, the powder was mixed with water, macerated for 72 hours and filtered using Whatman filter paper. The resulting solution is utilized for subsequent formulation processes.

Fig.11: Extraction of *Hibiscus Rosa sinensis*

INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY (10GM)
PUMPKIN EXTRACT	1.4ml
HIBISCUS EXTRACT	0.2ml
ROSEMARY OIL	0.8ml
BEES WAX	3.2gm
LIQUID PARAFFIN	10ml
BORAX	0.16gm
METHYL PARABIN	0.04gm
PROPYL PARABEN	0.04gm
WATER	q.s

Table 1: Formulation of the cream (w/o)

PROCEDURE FOR CREAM FORMULATION:

1. The W/O type of cream was prepared using 2 phases.
2. All the active pharmaceutical ingredients and excipients were measured accurately.
3. The oil phase was prepared by melting beeswax along with liquid paraffin and active drug rosemary oil extract by maintaining 70°C temperature.
4. Similarly, an aqueous phase was prepared by heating borax, methyl paraben, propyl paraben, hibiscus flower extract and pumpkin pulp extract with sufficient water by maintaining 70°C temperature.
5. When the 2 phases attain 70°C temperature, the aqueous phase was gradually introduced into the oil phase while continuous stirring until the cream consistency is attained.

6. Rosemary oil itself acts as a perfume for the formulation.
7. The cream was stirred well and packed and stored in a well-closed container.
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Formulation :1

PHYTOCHEMICAL TEST**A. TEST FOR ALKALOIDS**

Reagent: Dragendroff's reagent.

Procedure:

- Add a few drops extract and few drops of dragendroff's reagent.
- Appearance of brownish colour.
- Presence of alkaloids.

B. TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS**Reagent:** Dilute ammonia and concentrated sulfuric acid.**Procedure:**

- Add a 2 ml of extract to a few drops of ammonia.
- Add concentrated H₂SO₄ to the mixture.
- Appearance of yellow colour.
- Presence of flavonoids.

C. TEST FOR SAPONINS**Reagents:** Distilled water**Procedure:**

- Shake 2 mL of extract with 5 mL of distilled water in a test tube.
- Shake vigorously for 5 minutes.
- Formation of a persistent froth (foam) that lasts for at least 10-15 minutes indicates the presence of saponins.

D. TEST FOR TANNINS

Reagents: 1% Ferric chloride (FeCl₃)

- **Procedure:**

Add 2 mL of extract to a test tube.

Add a few drops of 1% ferric chloride.

Formation of a dark blue, green, or blackish color.

Presence of tannins.

E. TEST FOR PHENOLS (Ferric Chloride Test)

Reagents: 1% Ferric chloride (FeCl₃) **PHYTOCHEMICAL TEST**

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Formation of a dark blue, green, or blackish color.

Presence of tannins.

E. TEST FOR PHENOLS (Ferric Chloride Test)

- **Reagents:** 1% Ferric chloride (FeCl₃)

- **Procedure:**
 - Add 2 mL of extract to a test tube.
 - Add 1 mL of 1% ferric chloride.
 - Appearance of a deep blue, purple, or green colour. Presence of phenolic compound.

Fig.14:PHYTO CHEMICAL TEST

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

1. Physical appearance:

The physical appearance of the cream can be observed by its colour, roughness and was graded.

2. Homogeneity:

The formulation was tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch.

3. Washability:

The ease of removal of the cream was evaluated by washing the slide with tap water.

4. Afterfeel:

Emollience, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amount of cream was checked.

5. pH measurement:

The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution. About 0.5gm of cream was weighed and dissolved in 50ml of distilled water and its pH was measured using digital pH meter.

6. Dyetest:

The amaranth dye is mixed with the cream. A drop of the cream is placed on a microscope slide, covered with a cover slip, and examined under a microscope. If the dispersed globules appeared, then the cream is of the water-in-oil (w/o) type. In contrast, if the dispersed globules appear colorless, the cream is of the oil-in-water (o/w) type.

7. Spreadability:

Adequate amount of sample is taken between two glass slides and a weight of 100 gm is applied on the slides for 5 minutes.

Spreadability can be expressed as,

$$S = m \cdot l / t$$

Where,

m = weight applied to upper slide. l = length moved on the glass slide.

t = time taken.

8. Acid value:

A 10g sample of the substance was dissolved in an accurately weighed 50ml mixture of equal volumes of alcohol and solvent ether. The flask was connected to a reflux condenser and slowly heated until the sample dissolved completely. Then, 1ml of phenolphthalein was added, and the solution was titrated with 0.1N NaOH until a faint pink color appeared after shaking for 30 seconds.

$$\text{Acid value} = n \cdot 5.61 / w$$

Where,

n = the no. of ml of 0.1N KOH solution. w = the weight of substance in gram.

9. Saponification value:

2 grams of the substance were refluxed with 25 mL of 0.5 N alcoholic KOH for 30 minutes. To this mixture, 1 mL of phenolphthalein was added and it was titrated immediately with 0.5N HCl. Note the reading as 'a'. Repeat the operation, omitting the substance being examined and note the reading as 'b'.

$$\text{Saponification value} = (b - a) \cdot 28.05 / w$$

Where,

w = weight of substance in grams.

a = volume of titre in ml.

b = represents volume of blank in ml.

10. Anti-oxidant property:

The DPPH assay is conducted. Briefly, 80 µl of DPPH solution is mixed with various concentrations of the test solution and HPLC-grade methanol to a final volume of 240 µl. The reference standards are tested at concentrations ranging from 30 to 1.25 µg/ml, while the test samples are evaluated at concentrations from 320 to 10 µg/ml. The reaction mixture is incubated at 25°C for 15 minutes. Absorbance is then measured at 517 nm using a semi-automatic analyzer. A control reaction is performed without the test sam

PHYSICAL APPEARANCE

The morphological evaluation of cream is shown in the table. The produced formulation is pleasant and well acceptable flavour makes them ideal for cosmetic formulations. Smoothness and texture was suitable for cosmetic formulation.

Formulation(F)	Appearance	Colour	Odour	Texture
F1	Clear	Buffcolour	Aromatic	Smooth
F2	Clear	Buffcolour	Aromatic	Smooth

Table2: Organoleptic parameters

Fig.19: Physical appearance of cream

5. HOMOGENEITY

All formulations produced uniform distribution of extracts in cream. This was confirmed by visual appearance and by touch. The appearance and touch of the cream was good.

6. WASHABILITY

Washability test was carried out by applying small amount of cream on slid then washing with tap water. The observations are as follows.

Formulation(F)	Washability
F1	Easily washable
F2	Easily washable

Table3: Washability parameters

6. AFTERFEEL

The cream was applied to ascertain whether it's greasy or not.

Formulation(F)	Results
F1	Greasy

F2	Non greasy
----	------------

Table4:Afterfeeeffects

7. MEASUREMENT OF PH

pH of the formulations was measured using digital pH meter. The polyherbal cream formulations show the pH in the range from 6.82 to 6.98.

Formulation (F)	pH			Average pH
	Trial1	Trial 2	Trial 3	
F1	6.82	6.79	6.83	6.81
F2	6.82	6.84	6.84	6.83

Table5: pH of cream

SPREADABILITY

The sample was taken between two glass slides and a weight of 100g was applied on the slides for 5 minutes and by using the formula, the value of Spreadability for the formulations was calculated. The Spreadability value for the formulations was found to be in the range 52-76 g.cm/5min.

Formulation (F)	Spreadability (g.cm/5min)			Average Spreadability
	Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	
F1	60	62	60	60.67
F2	56	52	58	55.33

Table6: Spreadability of Cream

ACID VALUE

Acid value of the formulated cream was found to be in satisfactory values. Acid value is defined as the number of milligrams of KOH required to neutralize 1 gm of oil or fat. It indicates the amount of free fatty acid present in sample. If there are no fatty acids present, the oil or fat is of good quality, if there are more fatty acids present, it indicates the fat or oil has become rancid (hydrolysis of oil or fat).

The result of acid value of all formulation of cream are presented in below table and showed satisfactory values.

Formulation(F)	Acid value(mg KOH/g)
F1	3.19
F2	2.73

Table7: Acid Value

Fig.23:AcidvaluetestforCream

8. SAPONIFICATION VALUE

Saponification value for the formulated creams was found to be in satisfactory values. Saponification value is the number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide (KOH) or sodium hydroxide (NaOH) required to saponify one gram of fat under the conditions specified.

It is a measure of the average molecular weight (or chain length) of all the fatty acids present in the sample in form of triglycerides. The higher the saponification value, the lower the fatty acids average length, the lighter the mean molecular weight of triglycerides and vice versa.

The result saponification value of all formulation of cream are presented in below table and showed satisfactory values.

Formulation(F)	Saponificationvalue(KOH/g)
F1	150.90
F2	132.95

Table8:SaponificationValue

Fig.24:Saponification Test for Cream

10.DPPH RADICAL SCAVENGING ASSAY DPPH ANTI-OXIDANT ASSAY

The generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) beyond the antioxidant capacity of the biological system gives rise to oxidative stress. Free radical oxidative stress has been implicated in the pathogenesis of a variety of human diseases such as atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, inflammation, cancer and AIDS [48]. Antioxidants are a group of substances which, when present at low concentrations, in relation to oxidizable substrates, significantly inhibit or delay oxidative processes, while often being oxidized themselves. Antioxidants may exert their effect on biological systems by different mechanisms including electron donation (as reducing agents), metal ion chelation (thereby eliminating potential free radicals), sparing of antioxidants (co-antioxidants) [49]. Antioxidants lower the burden of free radicals and they have the ability to take up the free radicals and reduce the free radical and make it stable.

The DPPH scavenging assay is a simple chemical experiment for the primary evaluation of any compound for its simplicity and low cost for free radical scavenging activity [50, 51].

Principle:

DPPH [1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl] is a stable free radical with purple colour. Antioxidants reduces DPPH to 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazine, colorless compound which is measured at an absorbance of 517nm. 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazine, colorless compound which is measured at an absorbance of 517 nm.

Reagents:

- (i) DPPH (EEC No. 217-591-8, Sigma, USA), store at less than 0°C.
- (ii) Methanol, HPLC grade (Ranbaxy Chemicals).
- (iii) **Inhibitor(reference standard):** Ascorbic acid
- (iv) **Preparation of working solutions: 32mg/ml stock DPPH:** 1mg/ dissolved in 6 ml HPLC grade methanol.
- (v) **Procedure:**

DPPH assay is carried out as per the method of . [52]. In brief, 80µl of DPPH solution; various concentration of test solution and quantity sufficient to 240 µl with HPLC grade methanol. The different concentrations tested for reference standard are 30 -1.25µg/ml. The different concentrations tested for test samples are, 320-10 µg/ml. The reaction mixture is mixed and incubated at 25°C for 15 minutes. The absorbance is measured at 517nm using semiauto analyzer. A control reaction is carried out without the test sample.

Calculations:

Calculating percentage growth inhibition:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(\text{OD of Control} - \text{OD of Sample}) \times 100}{\text{OD of Control}}$$

Results:

	Conc μ M	OD@517	%Inhibition	IC50
Ascorbic acid	Control	0.827	0.00	
	1.125	0.680	17.78	
	3.25	0.574	30.59	10.68
	7.5	0.455	44.98	
	15	0.166	79.93	
	30	0.137	83.43	
	Conc μ M	OD@517	% Inhibition	IC 50
Cold cream	0	0.818	0.00	
	10	0.558	31.78	
	20	0.547	33.13	
	40	0.502	38.63	192.3
	80	0.466	43.03	
	160	0.406	50.37	
	320	0.319	61.00	

Table.9: Comparison between Ascorbic acid and Cream for antioxidant property.

Conclusion for Antioxidant activity:

The cold cream demonstrated antioxidant activity in the DPPH assay, with an IC₅₀ value of

192.3 µM. This indicates that the cold cream has a **moderate** ability to neutralize free radicals.

The percentage inhibition of the cold cream increased with concentration, reaching 61.00% at 320 µM. These results suggest that while the cold cream does possess antioxidant properties, it is less effective than ascorbic acid, which showed high antioxidant activity with an IC₅₀ value of 10.68 µM.

2. SUMMARY:

- The extraction of the chosen herbal plants was carried out to extract the active constituents
- The samples were then tested for its compatibility through FTIR tests
- The W/O cream was formulated by separately heating the oil phase and the aqueous phase to 70°C, then gradually combined while stirring until a cream consistency was achieved, the cream was then packed and stored.
- The cream's evaluation parameters were assessed

for its physical appearance, homogeneity, washability, after feel, pH, type, spreadability, acid and saponification values, and antioxidant properties through various tests.

- The evaluated results were documented
- The DPPH assay was carried out to evaluate the antioxidant activity by mixing DPPH with test solutions at various concentrations.
- The cold cream formulation combined pumpkin pulp, hibiscus flower extract, and rosemary oil, enhancing its efficacy with vitamins, antioxidants, and anti-inflammatory properties. These herbal plants have been used as home remedies from ancient period as it possesses potent activity
- The present study highlights the potential of herbal ingredients in skin care, promoting both cosmetic needs and skin health. The successful formulation of the polyherbal cold cream advances the integration of traditional herbal knowledge with modern cosmetic science, encouraging further exploration of natural resources.

8) CONCLUSION:

In this research, the formulation and evaluation of a polyherbal antioxidant cold cream using extracts from pumpkin pulp, hibiscus flower, and rosemary oil were successfully achieved. The study highlighted the significance of utilizing natural ingredients in cosmetic preparations, which offer not only enhanced skin benefits but also minimize the risks associated with synthetic components. Through rigorous evaluation, including FTIR studies, pH analysis, Spreadability, and antioxidant assessments, the developed cold cream demonstrated desiring results in terms of its topical application.

The incorporation of pumpkin pulp, rich in vitamins and antioxidants, hibiscus flower extract, known for its skin-soothing and anti-inflammatory properties, and rosemary oil, with its potent antioxidant activity, contributed to the overall efficacy of the formulation. The cold cream exhibited desirable characteristics such as homogeneity, good Spreadability, and a favourable pH, making it suitable for various skin types.

This study highlights the potential of herbal ingredients in skincare products, which not only improve appearance but also support skin health. The results encourage more research into herbal cosmetics and the use of other natural resources to improve skincare. The creation of this polyherbal cold cream is a step forward in combining traditional herbal knowledge with modern cosmetic science.

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